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Research Article

**THE OUTCOMES OF THE PATIENTS TREATED
FIBRINOLYTIC TREATMENT FOR MYOCARDIUM WITH ST-
SEGMENT ELEVATION INFARCTION (STEMI) AND
CONDUCTED A CORONARY ANGIOGRAPHY**¹Dr Muhammad Aun Ali Khan Sial, ²Dr M. Awais Altaf Khan Balouch, ³Dr Benazeer¹Services Hospital Lahore²Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur³Medical Officer in Rahnuma Family Planning Association of Pakistan**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Background: We intended to look at results of patients got fruitful fibrinolytic treatment (FT) for ST-section raised myocardial localized necrosis (STEMI) and performed coronary angiography (CAG) inside 24 - 72 h or after 72 h. **Methods:** Between March 2013 and November 2014, 76 STEMI patients got effective FT and performed CAG > 24 h remembered for the investigation. Patients were separated into two gatherings according to the time-span from FT admission to CAG performing (Group-1, 24 - 72 h (n = 29), Group-2, > 72 h (n = 47)). Our momentum research directed at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. The essential end was major unfriendly cardiovascular occasions (MACE) characterized as cardiovascular passing, non-lethal myocardial localized necrosis, and cardiovascular breakdown.

Results: The meantime of patients were 56 ± 11.4 years old (27.6% female). CAG performed inside mean 2.17 ± 0.38 days in the Group-1 and 2.9 ± 11.5 days in the Group 2 ($P < 0.001$). At present moment development (a half year), MACE rate was higher in Group-2 (21.3%) than Group-1(13.8%), however it was not measurably critical ($P = 0.661$). The pace of MACE was 37.9% in Group-1 and 38.3% in Group-2 ($P = 0.974$) in the long haul development (middle: 57 months). In general, cardiovascular death rate was 7.9%, the re-dead tissue rate was 19.7% and cardiovascular breakdown was 17.1% in long haul development, and there was no critical contrast between gatherings. **Conclusion:** Present examination has demonstrated that presentation of CAG after 24 h of fruitful FT, inside 24 - 74 h or > 72 h, didn't indicated any distinction in term of MACE both in short and long haul development.

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INTRODUCTION:

Early reperfusion in patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) has been shown to improve clinical outcomes. Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) represents the gold standard reperfusion treatment of the occluded epicardial arteries [1]. However, fibrinolytic treatment (FT) still remains the gold standard option, where primary PCI cannot be performed in the recommended time [2]. Relevant guidelines for the management of STEMI published recommend to perform coronary angiography (CAG) and if necessary, PCI within 24 h after successful FT [3]. Also, same guidelines recommend to do not perform CAG 2 or 3 h after successful FT. However, many patients do not perform PCI after successful FT in the recommended time interval since many different reasons. Although many previous studies determined the advantageous of early PCI strategy (< 24 h) after successful FT, few studies published concerning the results of exceeding 24 h from successful FT to CAG [4]. Also, long-term benefits of CAG after the recommend time interval are not clear. On this background, we aimed to compare the short and long-term outcomes of STEMI patients who received successful FT and did not perform CAG within 24 h and underwent CAG within 24 - 72 h or after 72 h [5].

METHODOLOGY:

Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020., all consecutive patients with the diagnosis of STEMI who were submitted to FT as primary strategy of reperfusion and did not perform CAG within 24 h after successful FT were included in the study. ST-segment elevated myocardial infarction (STEMI) was defines as following criteria: ST-segment elevation $\geq 0.1\text{mV}$ in two or more leads (0.2 mm for V1 - V3) or a new-onset left bundle branch block on an electrocardiogram, and typical ongoing ischemic chest pain for longer than 30 min [7]. The study was designed as prospective and observational. Patients who performed rescue PCI in the context of an unsuccessful TT (without reduction of ST-segment elevation, persistent chest pain for 90 min after initiation of thrombolysis or hemodynamic instability) were excluded. Moreover, patients who were < 18 years old or > 85 years old, or whose symptoms of myocardial infarction present for > 12 h, pregnancy, standard exclusion criteria for FT, and having history of heart failure were excluded from the study [1].

All patients received standard weight-adjusted dose fibrin specific thrombolytic agent within 10 min after

the first medical contact in emergency service. Also, all patients received aspirin 300 mg orally, clopidogrel 300 mg on the first day, and enoxaparin 30 mg intravenously followed by a subcutaneous dose of 1 mg/kg repeated every 12 h up to hospital discharge or revascularization for a maximum of 7 days [3]. In addition, all patients received beta-blockers, statin and angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors unless contraindication. Also, all patients received clopidogrel 75 mg daily for 12 months at the discretion of the treating physician.

Patients who were newly diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (DM) or were already on anti-diabetic therapy, or whose fasting plasma glucose ≥ 126 mg/dL were identified as diabetic [8]. Hypertension was defined as blood pressure (BP) $\geq 140/90$ mm Hg or the use of antihypertensive medication. Smoking was defined as smoking ≥ 1 cigarettes a day for at least 1 year, without an attempt to quit. Dyslipidemia, defined as total cholesterol ≥ 174 mg/dL or on the treatment with lipid-lowering drugs. Heart failure was diagnosed based on relevant guidelines of European Society of Cardiology [9]. Routine echocardiography was performed before discharge (Vivid-7, GE Healthcare) in the line of American Echocardiography Society guideline [10]. All routine laboratory parameters were recorded in planned control from hospital digital system. The researchers adhered to the principles of Helsinki Declaration throughout the study and the protocol of the study was approved by the Ethical Committee of Mayo Hospital Faculty of Medicine.

Statistical analyses:

Statistical analyses were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0) for Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Continuous data were presented as means and standard deviation. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to evaluate whether the continuous variables were normally distributed. Differences in continuous variables between the two groups were determined by Student's *t*-test or Mann-Whitney U-test. Categorical variables were summarized as percentages and were compared by the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. A survival analysis between the two groups was performed using the Kaplan-Meier method with a log-rank analysis. A *P* value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Totally 76 patients were included in the study, and all patients were followed for a median 57 months (interquartile range 48 - 69 months). The baseline clinical features of patients were summarized in

Table 1. The mean age of patients were 56 ± 11.4 years old (27.6% female). There were no significant differences between groups in term of clinical characteristics and laboratory parameters except family history of coronary artery disease (Group-1: 37.9% vs. Group-2: 12.8%; $P = 0.001$), diabetes mellitus (Group-1: 31.0% vs. Group-2: 8.5%; $P = 0.025$), and left ventricular ejection fraction (Group-1: $53.4 \pm 8.7\%$ vs. Group-2: $46.0 \pm 9.2\%$; $P = 0.003$). Vast majority of patient received FT within 3 h of symptom onset (Table 2). All patients in both groups were referred to CAG; the procedure was delayed by a mean time of 2.17 ± 0.38 days in the Group-1 and 2.9 ± 11.5 days in the Group 2 ($P < 0.001$). The total number of PCI procedures was similar between groups (Table 2). At discharge, 100% of patients were prescribed aspirin, 100% clopidogrel, 98.7 % statins, 93.4% beta-blockers, and 89.5% angiotensin converter enzyme or angiotensin receptor blocker, with no difference between groups. At 6 months, medication was unchanged (Table 3). The clinical outcomes at short-term (6 months) and long-term (median 57 months) follow-up were listed in Table 4. At short-

term follow-up, MACE rate was higher in Group-2 than Group-1 but it was not statistically significant (21.3% vs. 13.8%; $P = 0.661$, respectively). Also, overall cardiac mortality rate was 1.3%, the re-infarction was 9.2%, and heart failure was 14.5% at 6 months follow-up and similar between groups (Table 4). Overall, the rate of the MACE was 38.2% in long-term follow-up. The rate of MACE was 37.9% in Group-1 and 38.3% in Group-2 ($P = 0.974$). In addition, overall cardiac mortality rate was 7.9%, the re-infarction rate was 19.7% and heart failure was 17.1% in long-term follow-up; and there were no significant difference between groups (Table 4). The MACE-free survivals across the groups are shown in Figure 1. Predicting survival with a combination of cardiovascular death, non-fatal myocardial infarction, and heart failure showed no significant difference in survival between groups.

DISCUSSION:

The present study has shown that performing CAG after successful FT within 24 - 72 h or after 72 h did not cause differ-

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Study Population

Variable	All patients (n = 76)	Group-1 (n = 29)	Group-2 (n = 47)	P
Age (years), (mean $\pm$ SD)	56 ± 11.4	54.8 ± 11.2	57.4 ± 11.5	0.354
Female, n, (%)	21 (27.6)	6 (20.7)	15 (31.9)	0.424
Hospitalization time (days)	7.0 ± 4.0	7.3 ± 5.8	6.8 ± 2.4	0.661
Hypertension, n, (%)	27 (35.5)	12 (41.4)	15 (31.9)	0.402
Diabetes mellitus, n, (%)	13 (17.1)	9 (31.0)	4 (8.5)	0.025
Hyperlipidemia, n, (%)	14 (18.4)	4 (13.8)	10 (21.3)	0.414
Current smoker, n, (%)	66 (86.8)	24 (82.8)	42 (89.4)	0.408
History of CAD, n, (%)	9 (11.8)	2 (6.9)	7 (14.9)	0.469
Family history of CAD, n, (%)	17 (22.4)	11 (37.9)	6 (12.8)	0.001
Systolic BP (mm Hg)	137 ± 27	134 ± 17	140 ± 32	0.344
Diastolic BP (mm Hg)	80 ± 16	79 ± 11	82 ± 19	0.521
Heart rate (per minute)	76 ± 14	73 ± 14	78 ± 14	0.176
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	14 ± 1.6	14 ± 1.4	14 ± 1.7	0.51
Hematocrit (%)	41.3	41.4 ± 3.8	41.3 ± 4.7	0.87
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.89 ± 0.23	0.91 ± 0.27	0.88 ± 0.2	0.67
Aspartate aminotransferase (U/L)	27.3 ± 20.9	51 ± 92	59 ± 78	0.95
Alanine aminotransferase (U/L)	50.3 ± 83	28 ± 20.3	27 ± 21	0.83
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	191 ± 40	192 ± 42	191 ± 37	0.93
LDL-C (mg/dL)	121 ± 36	119 ± 34	122 ± 37	0.66
HDL-C (mg/dL)	38 ± 10	38 ± 11	39 ± 9	0.68
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	179 ± 95	194 ± 123	169 ± 74	0.27
LVEF (%)	48.6 ± 9.6	53.4 ± 8.7	46.0 ± 9.2	0.003

MACE rate both in short and long-term follow-up. Also there were no significant different between groups in term of secondary end points, cardiovascular death, re-infarction, and heart failure [6].

Nowadays, performance of a routine early CAG within 24 h is recommended after successful FT, if there are no contain- dictations [7]. In case of unsuccessful thrombolysis patients should undergo immediate CAG and rescue PCI [8]. Many previous studies have shown that an early routine CAG after successful FT reduced the rate of recurrent ischemia and re-infarction, compared with a watchful waiting strategy [9]. Although these studies have variable time windows between FT and CAG, all of them were less than 24 h. In this context, the time window from FT to CAG is 2 - 24 h in recent guide- line of European Society of Cardiology and 2 or 3 - 24 h in American Heart Association guideline with a IIa level of recommendation [10].

Table 2. Procedural Characteristics

Variable	All patients (n = 76)	Group-1 (n = 29)	Group-2 (n = 47)	P
Symptom onset to first medical contact				
< 1 h	47 (61.8)	19 (65.5)	28 (59.6)	0.873
1 - 3 h	23 (30.3)	8 (27.6)	15 (31.9)	
> 3 h	6 (7.9)	2 (6.9)	4 (8.5)	
Coronary angiography performed	70 (100)	29 (100)	47 (109)	NS
Time from FT to CAG	8.86 ± 10.4	2.17 ± 0.38	12.9 ± 11.5	< 0.001
PCI performed	69 (90.8)	26 (89.7)	43 (91.5)	0.788
Femoral access	70 (100)	29 (100)	47 (109)	NS

CAG: coronary angiography; FT: fibrinolytic treatment; PCI: percutaneous coronary intervention.

Table 3. Medication at Discharge and 6 Months Follow-Up

	All patients (n = 76)	Grup-1 (n = 29)	Grup-2 (n = 47)
Medication at discharge			
Aspirin, n, (%)	76 (100)	29 (100)	47 (100)
Clopidogrel, n, (%)	76 (100)	29 (100)	47 (100)
Statins, n, (%)	75 (98)	29 (100)	46 (98)
ACEI, n, (%)	68 (89)	26 (90)	42 (90)
Beta blockers, n, (%)	71 (93)	26 (90)	45 (96)
PPI, n, (%)	68 (89)	28 (96)	40 (85)
Medication at 6 months ^a			
Aspirin, n, (%)	75 (100)	29 (100)	46 (100)
Clopidogrel, n, (%)	73 (97)	29 (100)	44 (95)
Statins, n, (%)	75 (100)	29 (100)	46 (100)
ACEI, n, (%)	68 (90)	25 (86)	42 (93)
Beta blockers, n, (%)	72 (96)	27 (93)	45 (97)
PPI, n, (%)	68 (90)	25 (86)	43 (95)

^aOne patient in Group-2 died at the fourth month. ACEI: angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor.

Many previous studies determined the advantages of early PCI strategy (< 24 h) after successful FT, however there are few studies published concerning the results of exceeding 24 h time window from successful FT to CAG. In their study Costa et al [4] have shown that performing CAG outside of the 24 h time interval did not lead to higher in hospital mortality. In addition, the writing committee of American Heart Association guideline of management of STEMI believes that performing CAG beyond 24 h after successful FT likely will continue to benefit those patients with a patent but stenotic infarct artery. In stable patients who do not perform CAG within 24 h, CAG can be considered as part of a routine pharmacoinvasive or ischemia-guided approach > 24 h after administration of FT. However, the time-interval after > 24 h is not clear. Moreover, to our best knowledge, there is no clinical study that evaluated the both short and long-term results of CAG performing > 24 h after successful FT. In this context, to clarify the time intervals and evaluated the short and long-term results of CAG after > 24 h, we defined two-time interval as early (24 - 72h) and late (> 72h). We have shown that there were no significant differences between two time-intervals in term of MACE both in short and long-term follow-up. Similarly, there were no significant differences between groups in secondary end points; cardiovascular death, re-infarction, and heart failure and event-free survival.

Table 4. Clinical Outcomes of Short and Long-Term Follow-Up

Variable	All patients (n = 76)	Group-1 (n = 29)	Group-2 (n = 47)	P
Short-term follow-up (6 months)				
Death, n, (%)	1 (1.4)	0	1 (2.1)	NS
Re-infarction, n, (%)	7 (9.5)	2 (6.9)	7 (10.6)	0.295
Heart failure, n, (%)	11 (14.6)	3 (10.3)	8 (17)	0.422
MACE, n, (%)	14 (18.4)	4 (13.8)	10 (21.3)	0.661
Long-term follow-up (median 57 months)				
Death, n, (%)	6 (7.9)	1 (3.4)	5 (10.6)	0.398
Re-infarction, n, (%)	15 (19.7)	5 (17.2)	10 (21.3)	0.668
Heart failure, n, (%)	13 (17.1)	7 (24.1)	6 (12.8)	0.201
MACE, n, (%)	29 (38.2)	11 (37.9)	18 (38.3)	0.974

Figure 1. Kaplan-Meier analysis freedom from MACE.

CONCLUSIONS:

In present study, it was shown that performance of coronary angiography in patients with STEMI after 24 h of successful FT, within 24 - 74 h or > 72 h, did not show any significant difference in term of MACE both in short and long-term follow-up.

REFERENCES:

1. Madan M, Halvorsen S, Di Mario C, Tan M, Westerhout CM, Cantor WJ, Le May MR, et al. Relationship between time to invasive assessment and clinical outcomes of patients undergoing an early invasive strategy after fibrinolysis for ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction: a patient-level analysis of the randomized early routine invasive clinical trials. *JACC Cardiovasc Interv.* 2015;8(1Pt B):166-174.
2. Thygesen K, Alpert JS, Jaffe AS, Simoons ML, Chaitman BR, White HD, Joint ESCAAHAWHFTfUDoMI, et al. Third universal definition of myocardial infarction. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2012;60(16):1581-1598.
3. European Guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice (version 2012) The Fifth Joint Task Force of the European Society of Cardiology and Other Societies on Cardiovascular Disease Prevention in Clinical Practice (constituted by representatives of nine societies and by invited experts). Developed with the special contribution of the European Association for Cardiovascular Prevention & Rehabilitation (EACPR). *European Journal of Preventive Cardiology* 2012;19:585-667.
4. McMurray JJ, Adamopoulos S, Anker SD, Auricchio A, Bohm M, Dickstein K, Falk V, et al. ESC guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of acute and chronic heart failure 2012: The Task Force for the Diagnosis and Treatment of Acute and Chronic Heart Failure 2012 of the European Society of Cardiology. Developed in collaboration with the Heart Failure Association (HFA) of the ESC. *Eur J Heart Fail.* 2012;14(8):803-869.
5. Lang RM, Bierig M, Devereux RB, Flachskampf FA, Foster E, Pellikka PA, Picard MH, et al. Recommendations for chamber quantification: a report from the American Society of Echocardiography's Guidelines and Standards Committee and the Chamber Quantification Writing Group, developed in conjunction with the European Association of Echocardiography, a branch of the European Society of Cardiology. *J Am Soc Echocardiogr.* 2005;18(12):1440-1463.
6. Cantor WJ, Fitchett D, Borgundvaag B, Ducas J, Heffernan M, Cohen EA, Morrison LJ, et al. Routine early angioplasty after fibrinolysis for acute myocardial infarction. *N Engl J Med.* 2009;360(26):2705-2718.
7. Scheller B, Hennen B, Hammer B, Walle J, Hofer C, Hilpert V, Winter H, et al. Beneficial effects of immediate stenting after thrombolysis in acute myocardial infarction. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2003;42(4):634-641.
8. Bohmer E, Hoffmann P, Abdelnoor M, Arnesen H, Halvorsen S. Efficacy and safety of immediate angioplasty versus ischemia-guided management after thrombolysis in acute myocardial infarction in areas with very long transfer distances results of the NORDISTEMI (NORwegian study on DIstrict treatment of ST-elevation myocardial infarction). *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2010;55(2):102-110.
9. Fernandez-Aviles F, Alonso JJ, Castro-Beiras A, Vazquez N, Blanco J, Alonso-Briales J, Lopez-Mesa J, et al. Routine invasive strategy within 24 hours of thrombolysis versus ischaemia-guided conservative approach for acute myocardial infarction with ST-segment elevation (GRACIA-1): a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet.* 2004;364(9439):1045-1053.
10. Armstrong PW, Committee WS. A comparison of pharmacologic therapy with/without timely coronary intervention vs. primary percutaneous intervention early after ST-elevation myocardial infarction: the WEST (Which Early ST-elevation myocardial infarction Therapy) study. *Eur Heart J.* 2006;27(13):1530-1538.